

Forensic steganalysis for identification of steganography software tools using multiple format image

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ABSTRACT

Today many steganographic software tools are freely available on the Internet, which helps even callow users to have covert communication through digital images. Targeted structural image steganalysers identify only a particular steganographic software tool by tracing the unique fingerprint left in the stego images by the steganographic process. Image steganalysis proves to be a tough challenging task if the process is blind and universal, the secret payload is very less and the cover image is in lossless compression format. A payload independent universal steganalyser which identifies the steganographic software tools by exploiting the traces of artefacts left in the image and in its metadata for five different image formats is proposed. First, the artefacts in image metadata are identified and clustered to form distinct groups by extended K-means clustering. The group that is identical to the cover is further processed by extracting the artefacts in the image data. This is done by developing a signature of the steganographic software tool from its stego images. They are then matched for steganographic software tool identification. Thus, the steganalyser successfully identifies the stego images in five different image formats, out of which four are lossless, even for a payload of 1 byte. Its performance is also compared with the existing steganalyser software tool.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Image steganalysis is the art of uncovering the presence of secret in a mundane image. The digital era has provided numerous freeware steganography tools online that help novice users to embed data easily without any prior knowledge of steganographic algorithms [1]-[3]. This makes masked communication as a piece of cake to even an obvious illicit user. A simple analysis on existing steganography tools reveals the fact that most of them use lossless 24-bit image formats. The common among them are BMP, GIF, PNG and TIFF formats. Among them, BMP image format is the most widely used, because it provides a large area of hiding (implying large payload) with less probability of detection (less pixel change rate) in spite of its uncompressed data. The lossy JPEG images are least preferred because these image types are easily distorted (low payload; high pixel change rate) and detection is therefore much simpler. Thus, in general steganalysis process depends on cover image format and payload.

Most of the work carried out in the literature concentrates on the finding the artefacts produced by the

steganographic algorithm on the cover image data as a result of embedding. Universal steganographic software tool identification is scarcely reported in current literature. This is because every steganographic software tool has an underlying algorithm and detection of algorithm is sufficient for the detection of cover or stego images. However, a good deal of steganographic software tool uses the least significant bit (LSB) encoding though it is simple for digital image steganography. This makes the steganographic software tool identification as a challenging one, since the method of steganalysis of algorithm found in literature cannot be used here [4]-[15].

A wide range of simple targeted steganographic software tool identification is reported in literature. The pioneer work in the field reported that some tools leave a signature which can be exploited to identify the tool and stego-image [16]. They proved it for a set of steganographic software tools (S-Tools, Syscop, MandelSteg, etc) which used palette and fractal images. Westfeld and Pfitzmann [17] used the tools like EzStego v2.0b3, Jsteg v4, Steganos v1.5, and S-Tools v4.0 for detection by statistical steganalysis. Provos and Honeyman [18] later developed StegDetect to identify steganographic content and StegBreak to launch dictionary attack on those and retrieve the hidden content in JPEG images. Geetha *et al.* [19] identified watermarking and steganographic tools using an genetic-X-means classifier. Verma *et al.* [20] proposed a steganalysis technique on the basis of statistical observations on difference image histograms (DIH) for the reliable detection of classical least significant bit (LSB) steganography which measured the weak correlation between successive bit planes to construct a classifier for discrimination between stego-images and cover images. Sloan and Hernandez-Castro [21] reported the identification of openpuff in video steganalysis. All these were targeted (specific to single tool) and required patient scrutiny of the images manually which was time consuming and error prone.

An important work in this field was by [22] where they designed a fully automated, blind, media-type agnostic approach to steganalysis by bitwise analysis of header data and generated a signature for each tool. Though they reported their work to be media-type agnostic, the results reported were based on seven tools out of which five were of JPEG format, one in MP3 format and one in GIF format tools and a minimum of 10 stego images of each tool were used to generate the signature for the tool. This provided an insight into working out a universal steganalyser for steganographic software tool identification exploiting both artefacts in the image data and its metadata. Almost all current steganalysers require at least a little knowledge of the used steganographic software tools. Feeding the information may be a mammoth task comparing the number of tools available [23]. So a payload independent universal steganalyser is proposed that initially exploits the macroscopically changing fields of the image metadata and information from metadata to identify the tools by clustering. This helps in segregating most of the tools, while those similar to cover are further processed. This is done by forming a signature from stego images of those tools from artefacts present in their image data. The scope of the proposed universal steganalyser is limited to stego tools that work in these five image formats namely BMP, GIF, PNG, TIFF and JPEG.

The structure of this paper is as follows : Section 2. describes the structure of the Universal steganalyser; Section 3. presents the steganalysis using image header; Section 4. extends the steganalysis by comparing the signature generated for the steganographic software tool in image data; Section 5. measures and evaluates the technique experimentally; Section 6. concludes the work, and is followed by appendices and references.

2. PROPOSED UNIVERSAL STEGANALYSIS

The steganalysis of stego images from different steganographic software tools is done in two phases. In the first phase, the stego images are first distinguished based on one of the five image formats. Then, for each image format, certain fields or information from the fields of the header data are extracted. These features are then subjected to unsupervised clustering by means of extended K-Means. Extended K-Means clustering acts as pattern matching template to identify different steganographic software tools uniquely. Though this initial clustering identifies most of the steganographic software tools, it leaves space for steganalysis of steganographic software tools that take care of not disturbing the metadata while processing. The stego images from these steganographic software tools resemble cover images and are placed in the cluster as that of the cover. The second phase of steganalysis starts by taking these clusters. As a prerequisite for this phase, a signature is generated for each tool from the artefacts in image data. This signature is compared against the signature found in the stego images of the cluster. If a signature match is found, then the tool is identified. The block diagram of the proposed steganalyser is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Block diagram of the proposed steganalyser

3. STEGANALYSIS USING IMAGE HEADER ARTEFACTS

A great portion of literature in digital image forensic exploit header data for various purposes [24]. Here it is used for steganalysis of steganographic software tools.

3.1. Fields considered in each image format

As mentioned earlier the steganalyser is to exploit the vulnerable fields of image header to identify the tool. The fields that may lead to identification of the tools are detailed for each format [25]-[29].

3.1.1. BMP image format

The BMP images have a fixed byte format. The fields-bits per pixel, image data padding (last two bytes of 4 bytes of SizeofBitmap field) horizontal resolution, Vertical resolution is used since most steganographic software tool modify them. In addition, the actual size of BMP file derived from the fields is used. Thus, these five fields form features that are used for identifying tool in BMP images.

3.1.2. GIF image format

There are two version formats in GIF; 87a and 89a. The trailer field is used to find camouflage steganographic software tools that do not make a single change in image but insert the secret data after the image data. The version field in file header, the packed field of the global colour table in logical screen descriptor and the packed field of the local image descriptor which has the image and colour table data information are also used. Presence of graphic control, comment and plain text extension block, size of global and local colour table are also unique features to identify tool. Thus, these fields form the features to identify tools in GIF format.

3.1.3. JPEG image format

The JPEG format is dependent on the quality factor of the JPEG compression and thus can be used to distinguish not only tools but also algorithms. The fields that are exploited are as follows: JFIF version, density unit field in JFIF header, presence of data after last end of image (EOI) marker, presence of comment marker (COM), quantisation table length and location of Huffman table. These six information from header form the JPEG feature vector.

3.2. PNG image format

The PNG file format supports a number of chunks which help in tool identification. The presence of auxiliary chunk types like time-time of last modification, text-extensions and their cyclic redundancy check (CRC) are used to cluster tools. End of file is checked with IEND chunk field. Thus, the feature vector for PNG format is taken from these fields.

3.2.1. TIFF image format

The TIFF is supported by data in two ordering: little endian and big endian, which forms the first feature. Here again presence of additional tags like artist, copyright, hostcomputer, make, model, software or datetime indicate a tool. Presence of New SubFileType or SubFileType Tag can account for significant tool identification. In addition, the fields like Number of tags in image file directory, Number of StripOffset, and information derived from RowsPerStrip, StripOffsets, StripByteCounts and DataType fields to indicate data embedded at End of image are exploited as features for TIFF images.

3.3. Clustering algorithm

When the labels of the given data are unknown, unsupervised learning takes place through clustering. One simple form of clustering the given information is K-Means clustering. This clustering requires number of cluster (K) as input. The provision of number of clusters is not possible in a practical scenario. So an extension to the K-Means is made by repeating with the K-Means algorithm with increasing cluster numbers until the distance of each sample to its centroid is zero. Thus, the optimal number of clusters is determined. The pseudo code for the algorithm is given as below:

Algorithm extended KMeans

Input - Features and Number of Samples

Output - Optimized Number of clusters COUNT and the Clusters, CLUST

FOR COUNT = 1 to Number of samples

- Let Kmeans clustering of COUNT clusters based on city block distance with 5 cross validation be CLUST
- Let the within cluster distance of each cluster in CLUST be DIST
- IF DIST is equal to zero for all clusters
 - The optimal clusters and their number are found in CLUST and COUNT respectively; EXIT
- ELSE Continue

Within cluster distance of cluster is zero means exact match. Thus, the algorithm helps in identifying the exact tool's header signature which is later correlated with the tool.

4. STEGANALYSIS BY ARTEFACTS IN IMAGE DATA

The stego images of the steganographic software tool that do not modify the header or the metadata of the cover image cannot be detected by the above process. In order to identify those stego images and to ultimately reveal the tool, the artefacts left by the steganographic software tool in image data is considered. The metadata (stego key) about the steganographic process is in some way hidden inside the image data [16].

The fact is that the metadata is either hidden sequentially in the start or at the end of the image file or randomly. Even though the metadata may vary in byte level, it is found that at bit level, things do not change [22]. Things may be either the bit or its position. This is generated as a signature of the tool by examining its stego image data in bit level. The signature is generated from either first 100 pixels or the last 100 pixels depending on the tool and saved in signature library. This signature is compared with the bits of the stego image to be tested. A match implies the tool being used. The characteristic signature of WB Stego tool as an average of last 30 pixels over 50 images is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Average signature found in the last 30 pixels of 50 randomly selected BMP images, (a) WB stego BMP images, (b) Cover BMP images

Thus an automated approach for universal steganalysis of software tool is done by tracing the artefact left by the tool in both the image header and its data.

5. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

No benchmark steganographic tools exists for steganalysis. So to create a repository of stego images, steganographic software tools are downloaded from sites referred in [23] using images from sources Bossbase, McGill databases. Table 1 lists the different steganographic software tools used.

Table 1. List of steganographic software tools used with supporting image format

SNo	Steganographic software tool (version)	Supporting image formats
1	2pix v1.1 (2P)	BMP
2	BlindSide v0.9b (BS)	BMP
3	DeEgger Embedder v1.3.6 (DE)	BMP, GIF, JPEG, PNG, TIFF
4	F5 (F)	JPEG
5	File in File (Fi)	BMP
6	Gifshuffle (GS)	GIF
7	Hermatic system StegPNG trail version 11.01 (hs)	BMP, PNG
8	Hide & Reveal v1.7.0 (hi)	BMP, PNG, TIFF
9	Hide in Picture v2.1 (HI)	BMP, GIF
10	Image Hide v2.0 (IH)	BMP, PNG
11	Image Protector v3.6 (IP)	BMP
12	Invisible Secrets trail version4.0 (IS)	BMP, JPEG, PNG
13	JHide v1.0.0 (JH)	BMP, PNG, TIFF
14	JPHSwin V0.5 (JP)	JPEG
15	nsF5 (ns)	JPEG
16	Open Puff v4.00 (OP)	BMP, JPEG, PNG
17	Our Secret v2.5 (OS)	BMP, GIF, JPEG, PNG, TIFF
18	Outguess v0.2 (O)	JPEG
19	Secret Layer v.2.8.1 (SL)	BMP, JPEG, PNG
20	Silent Eye v0.4.1 (SE)	BMP, JPEG
21	SSuite Piscal (SP)	BMP, PNG
22	Steganofile v1.0 (SF)	BMP
23	Steghide v0.5-win32 (sh)	BMP, JPEG
24	S-Tools v4.0 (ST)	BMP, GIF
25	Steganography Tool (imgAuthServer) (I)	PNG
26	The Secret Code Breaker Steganography program v1.2 (5)	BMP
27	Third Eye v1.0 (TE)	BMP, GIF
28	Trojan v1.0 (T)	BMP, PNG, TIFF
29	Veneer (V)	BMP, GIF, JPEG, PNG, TIFF
30	Wb - Stego v4.3 (WS)	BMP
31	Xiao v2.6.1 (X)	BMP

For cover images, both images from clean source and internet are exploited. McGill Image database [30] which proves a challenging cover source for steganalysis is taken for clean images. Thus, the cover image database consists of 1000 images with random 500 from each source. They are basically either tiff or bmp format images. They are resized to 512×512 for simplicity. The cover images are then converted to five image formats namely BMP, TIFF, PNG, GIF and JPEG. For JPEG images, 100% compression ratio is used. A random 100 images from the cover source is chosen for each steganographic software tool to make the stego images for each format. Thus, a total of 6,500 (25×100 BMP, 7×100 GIF, 12×100 JPEG, 13×100 PNG, 6×100 TIFF) stego images are created. The secret data is random data ranging from 1 byte to maximum possible payload by the tool. 100 random cover images (CO) for each format is also taken (though a single cover image is enough). The experiment is carried out on the set up database. The results of first phase of steganalysis are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Scatter plot of clustering information from header data in various image formats, (a) PNG format, (b) GIF format, (c) TIFF format, (d) JPEG format, (e) BMP format

In this phase, it is noted that the steganographic software tool (DE,V,OS) that hide data at the end of image file are all clustered in separate group and are identified regardless of formats. Software specific to format (GS, IP, WB, BS) are largely difficult to identify, since care is taken by tool to leave no trace in header data. In steganographic software tool that support more than one format, at least one format is insecure (HR, HI, IS, ST, JH, OP, SL). Only one system (hs) that supports multiple format is not detectable in any of the formats. Also, it is verified that of all formats, identification of tool is very difficult in BMP because of its simple and short header, other formats have large information in header which in turn leads to loopholes or vulnerability. For the second phase, those images that resemble cover (stego images clustered along with cover) are fed as the input to the steganalyser and the results are tabulated as in Table 2.

It can be seen from Table 2 that almost all steganographic software tools store their metadata in the image data. And the signature of each tool is unique with no two tools having same signature. Also, this signature is present independent of image format. However, this phenomenon was absent in GIF format which may likely be due to the fact that GIF formats alter palette rather than data. Rarely some tools like BS, HI and ST handle it. Either they do not store meta data in its image or they are stored randomly.

Table 2. Experimental results for signature matching in image data of different steganalyser tools

S.No	Image format	Tool	Signature length (in bits) and location	Average signature match in %	
				True positive	False positive
1		S	14 Top	100	0
2		BS	No signature	0	0
3		HI	No signature	0	0
4		IH	145 Top	100	0
5		IP	83 Top	100	0
6		IS	101 Top	100	0
7	BMP	JH	58 Bottom	100	0
8		OP	24 Bottom	100	0
9		ST	No signature	0	0
10		WS	284 Bottom	100	0
11		hi	260 Top	100	0
12		hs	39 Bottom	100	0
13		sh	132 Bottom	100	0.7
14	GIF	GS		100	
15		O	60 Bottom	100	0
16	JPEG	OP	72 Bottom	100	0.25
17		SL	67 Bottom	100	0.25
18		sh	99 Bottom	100	0.75
19		JH	60 Bottom	100	0
20	PNG	hi	173 Top	100	0
21		hs	20 Bottom	100	0

Comparison of this steganalyser is done with existing freeware steganalyser namely StegSpy v2.1 [31], StegSecret also known as XStegSecretBeta v0.1 [32], StegExpose [33]. StegSpy claims to identify the following programs: Hiderman, hide and seek, masker, JPegX and Invisible Secrets. Following are the techniques and tools identified by StegSecret (PNG & TIFF formats not supported) : Tools - Camouflage V1.2.1, inThePicture v2, JPEGXv2.1.1, pretty good envelope PGE) v1.0, appendX v less than 4, Steganography v1.6.5, inPlainView, DataStash v1.5 and dataStealth v1.0. Techniques - EOF techniques, Visual Attacks, ChiSquare Attack and RS Attack. Sequential and Pseudorandom LSBs, uses BDAS v0.1 (steganography tools fingerprint DataBase) to detect more than 40 steganography tools. StegExpose (TIFF format not supported) is statistical tool for identifying LSB embedding in images. It employs ChiSquare attack, RS attack and primary set attacks to identify tool. These tools are used against generic cover, stego classification on the set up database. The results are noted in Table 3.

Table 3. Percentage of stego images identified by different steganalyser tools

Stegano graphic tool	Steg expose	Steg secret	Steg spy	Proposed steganalyser	Stegano graphic tool	Steg expose	Steg secret	Steg spy	Proposed steganalyser
BMP image format					JPEG Image format				
2P	30	0	30	100	DE	10	100	10	100
BS	0	0	5	0	F5	0	0	0	100
DE	20	100	50	100	IS	10	0	10	100
Fi	10	100	90	100	JP	20	0	0	100
hs	100	0	90	100	ns	10	0	0	100
hi	0	0	60	100	OP	0	0	10	100
HI	20	0	90	0	OS	10	100	0	100
IH	10	0	70	100	O	10	0	0	100
IS	100	0	30	100	SL	20	0	10	100
IP	10	0	60	100	SE	0	0	0	100
JH	0	0	60	100	sh	10	0	10	100
OP	70	0	50	100	V	0	100	0	100
OS	10	100	30	100	PNG image format				
SL	40	0	40	100	DE	0	0	50	100
SE	40	0	50	100	hs	100	0	10	100
SP	0	0	40	100	hi	60	0	20	100
SF	0	100	70	100	IH	0	0	20	100
sh	0	0	50	100	IS	0	0	30	100
ST	0	0	40	0	JH	0	0	20	100
5	0	0	60	100	OP	0	0	40	100
TE	0	10	50	100	OS	0	0	10	100
T	10	0	70	100	SL	50	0	40	100
V	0	100	50	100	SP	50	0	10	100
WS	10	0	40	100	I	10	0	0	100
X	0	70	40	100	T	0	0	0	100
GIF image format					V	0	0	60	100
DE	0	0	10	100	TIFF image format				
GS	0	0	0	0	DE	0	0	70	100
HI	0	0	0	100	hi	0	0	70	100
OS	10	100	20	100	JH	0	0	70	100
ST	0	0	0	100	OS	0	0	80	100
TE	0	0	40	100	T	0	0	50	100
V	10	100	20	100	V	0	0	70	100

6. CONCLUSION

In almost all the formats, the identification of tool by its stego image independent of payload is a major contribution of the proposed steganalyser over the statistical steganalyser which finds detection of stego images with payload less than 5% of the maximum capacity as an arduous task. The other facts that can be concluded from the experimentation are almost all tools leave a trace in either the header or the data of the stego image. BMP format has the least vulnerable header of all image formats and size of secret payload is irrelevant because it is not related to the image statistics but to the tool signature. Thus, this universal blind structural steganalyser is capable of identifying tools which leave their trace in the stego images irrespective of the size of secret payload. Conversely, this means that this method will not operate at all against implementations of algorithms that do not produce characteristic irregularities in their header (simple LSB batchwise processing) or store their metadata in the image BS. However, at large, a match against a stego signature can provide a useful indication that a particular tool may have been used and consequently an indication that the file may contain steganography. Also, this steganalyser produces a 100% match for a tool irrespective of payload which cannot be the case for other statistical steganalyser. So such universal structural steganalysers can effectively be deployed as the pre mechanisms to the existing steganalysis techniques and help to improve overall accuracy.

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